

Electronic Bank Fraud in Nigeria: The Need to Enhance Customers' Trust

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of electronic bank fraud on customers' trust in Nigeria with the aim of finding ways to enhance customers trust in the banking sector. Primary data was used for the study through structured questionnaire. The study employed logit regression as method to analyse the data. The result revealed that ATMF is significant and positively related to CT, MOBF and WEBF were insignificant and negatively related to CT while POSF exerted a positive and insignificant relationship with CT. Findings from the study further revealed that mobile fraud and website fraud posed more threat to customers' trust in electronic payment channels than ATM and POS. The study concluded that electronic fraud has significant relationship with customers' trust in Nigeria. The study therefore recommended that Banks should increase their security layers and ensure continuous enlightenment of customers on the need to safeguard their PINs. Bank customers should avoid replying unsolicited text messages and mails while the CBN should provide adequate security measures for various electronic payment channels so as to enhance customers' trust.

Keywords: *Electronic Fraud, Customers' trust, Automated Teller Machine, Mobile Banking, Web Purchases, Fraudsters, Bank Customer, Payment Channels.*

INTRODUCTION

The banking environment these days is more complex with the advancement in technology in the area of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) which has changed the nature of banking activities. Gone are the days when the banking system use ledgers in keeping customers records. During those days, customers were made to queue for many hours in the banking hall which is usually filled to its capacity by customers with different needs of financial services. With the adoption and updating of latest ICT facilities in the banking industry, the story has changed. Customers can now access banking services, pay utility bills without having to visit the service providers at the comfort of their rooms.

For instance, Olaleye and Fashina (2019) argued that practice of electronic banking has not only increased the volume of banking transactions but also improved service delivery to customers as well as improving the operational efficiency of banks. Many cutting-edge products and services have been developed which in turn have changed the ways customers interact and transact. The ease of doing business, transparency and swiftness that technology brought to the financial system in Nigeria are noteworthy. However, this development has brought about increase in the number of financial losses by banks through fraudulent activities with the aid of ICT by unscrupulous elements in the society.

Recently, the rise in the number of fraudulent activities going on in the Nigerian banking industry has become a worrisome development in the sector. The problem in recent time has posed a serious threat to the banking system especially the one that is done through the internet otherwise known as electronic fraud. This has reduced the efficiency of most banks thereby leading to distress. Bank distress is associated with the problem of illiquidity and insolvency. While insolvency connotes greater problem compared to illiquidity, the later could not be neglected because it is an ominous sign of insolvency. When the problem of illiquid persists for a longer period, it could lead bank to forcefully sell assets below their market value. Such force sales when large enough can lead to insolvency (Ajayi 2006). With increasing sophistication of fraudsters, the crime rate assumed to be in alarming proportions unless effective controls are put in place. Today in Nigeria, most deposit money banks spend huge amount of money as refund to customers whose money were lost through electronic fraud thereby causing a huge financial lost to the banks.

Electronic Fraud in Nigeria: Facts and Figures

In Nigeria, in spite of the regulatory activities and periodic bank examination by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC), there is still a growing concern about electronic fraud and other unethical practices in the banking industry. According to the CBN, the volume of electronic transactions in 2017 by the financial institutions in Nigeria was 1.4 billion valued at N97.4 trillion (Financial Nigeria 2018). This is higher than the volume recorded in 2016 where 869 million transactions

were processed with a value of N69.1 trillion. However, this increase has led to the rise in number of fraudulent activities in the banking sector whereby the complaints of electronic fraud received in 2015 were about 19,531 and rose to 25,043 in 2017.

Furthermore, Dipo Fatokun, director of banking and payment system in CBN said in a forum that whopping sum of N5.571 billion was lost between 2015 and 2017. Out of which the fraud carried out through the ATM increased from N355.89 million in 2015 to N497.643 million in 2017. More than 25,043 cases of fraud complaints were brought before the CBN in 2017 out of which over 13,715 were resolved by the CBN. This development has caused the deposit money bank to refund about N72.2 billion to different customers whose money were lost due to electronic fraud. Whereas, about 20,768 electronic fraud cases were brought before the apex bank in the first half of 2018 which cost the deposit money banks about N19.77 billion. This made known by CBN economic report for the first half of 2018 (The cable 2018).

According to the Director, Consumer Protection Department, Central Bank of Nigeria who predicted that the about N6.1 trillion will be lost to electronic banking fraud in Nigeria by 2021. However, it is believed that the fraud and forgery incidences were perpetrated by both bank staff and non-bank staff who most of the time find a way of getting unpermitted access by hacking into the accounts of unsuspecting bank customers. The Nation (2019) published that ATM and mobile channels recorded the highest incidence of fraud in 2018. Also, Business Insider SSA's analysis of the bank's financial statement for half-year 2018, showed that 44 ATM cases of fraud were recorded, 9 bank's staff fraud cases, 8 impersonation account, 45 stolen and forged instrument, 2 internet banking fraud while others fraudulent activities account for 43 cases.

The financial stability report signed by CBN Director, Financial Policy and Regulation Department, Kelvin Amugo said that in the less than 30-day period analysis, seven banks were not adequately funded, while in the 31 to 90-day period, nine banks had funding gaps. Arising from the above, seven banks failed the stress test (The Nation 2019)

The reports of year by year increase in electronic fraud attest to the fact that fraudsters do not grow weary. As the rate of advancement in technology through the introduction of more innovated products and services is increasing so also the rate of electronic fraud is increasing in Nigeria. Therefore, the determination and commitment of these fraudsters to continue to defraud people of their fund cannot be underrated within the financial system.

Dimensions and Channels of Electronic Fraud

There is no doubt that the advancement in financial technologies and the rise in different channels and modes of payment facilitate the rapid growth in the volume and value of electronic transactions in Nigeria. According to the work of Taiwo, Agwu, Babajide, Okafor and Isibor (2016) who believed that the numerous risks that financial institutions are exposed to reduced their ability to perform their duties effectively as a financial intermediary. In their opinion, fraud is one of such risks that have been a serious concern to both financial institutions and the regulatory authority. While Ibanichuka and Oko (2019) argued that the desire to reduce banks operating costs and improved financial performance has led to the deployment of electronic banking channels for various banking transactions. In order to align with what is obtainable globally, the Nigerian banking industry adopts modern ICT facilities to render various financial services to their customers. However, fraudsters are using it to defraud unsuspecting customers and banks resulting in huge financial loss.

Different methods such as counterfeiting, identity theft, card trapping, pharming, cloning, malware attack, BIN attack, skimming, phishing and carding are used to defraud and steal from users of electronic payment. The targets of electronic fraud include the individual bank customer, merchants, retailers, banking institutions, organisations and the government. Nobody is spared by these criminals. The major factors responsible for the high rate of fraud include the advent and extensive growth in computer technology and globalized economies supporting e-fraud, poor financial and regulatory framework, weak internal control system and societal attitude to achievement at all cost (Olaleye & Fashina 2019).

Ogbuji, Onuoha and Izogo (2012) opined that the ATM system of delivering banking services not only contribute to the increasing rate of bank fraud but equally lures Nigerians into profligate expenditure. Computer frauds according to Olaleye and Fashina (2019) can be carried out in different forms either by corrupting the program or breaking into the system via a remote sensor by a computer programmer or specialist.

However, majority of fraud committed in the banking sector in Nigeria are usually committed through electronics transfer and computer manipulation. Olaleye and Fashina (2019) highlighted the various channels through which electronic frauds are perpetrated this include: Smart card, electronic fund transfer, mobile telephone banking, personal computer, ATM internet banking channel, time bomb or trap door, scavenging, and software piracy.

Other means used by fraudsters are fake alerts, site cloning/ triangulation, hacking, phishing/brand spoofing, unauthorised messages, stealing of card pin, money laundering, account takeover fraud, debit card skimming, unauthorised withdrawal from customers account and so on.

Most of these criminal acts are perpetrated by skilled greedy data processing professionals whose skills can be channelled to more productive areas that will be beneficial to the larger society.

Electronic Fraud and Customers' Trust

Customer trust in the use of e-banking has been recognized by researchers as one of the key motive why a large percentage of consumers are still reluctant to adopt e-banking, most especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Recent development in the area of e-fraud in Nigeria financial sector has become an embarrassment to the nation which is obviously seen in the inability of the law enforcement agents to successfully track down culprits (Idolor 2010). This issue has gotten to a level at which many stakeholders are losing their trust and confidence in the sector.

Similarly, Popoola (2013) was of the opinion that despite of the numerous benefits offered by e-banking to the customers, still many customers are unwilling to accept the serves due to many trust related issues. He further noted that bank customers who are non-users of internet banking lack trust in internet banking and the users of internet banking have partial trust in it because of lack of security, bad reputation of banks, poor technology and lack of assuring policy or guarantee. On their part, Maruf, Rushami and Sany (2015) highlighted the factors responsible for the adoption of e-banking to include: perceived security, satisfaction and trust. Whereas, Aigbe and Akpojaro (2014) argued that the security levels of a payment system is related to fraud vulnerability which determines customers' confidence in the system. Kesharawani and Radhakrishna (2013) asserted that active and potential users of e-banking are scared and intimidated because of news arising from electronic frauds, electronic scams and phishing. They opined that users of electronic banking are apprehensive while using various channels of e-banking because of lack of adequate security.

From the foregoing, it has been established by various studies that security of electronic banking is significantly related to customers' trust. Also, the absence of it however is regarded as a serious barrier that can prevent people from using e-banking platform. However, KPMG (2013) asserted that only the service provider can crack the challenge of security in the usage of electronic banking in Nigeria for the country to enjoy the full benefits of electronic banking.

Empirical Investigations on Electronic Fraud in Nigeria

Studies in the area of electronic fraud and customers trust are relatively few and new. But with the numerous cases of online fraud recorded recently, this has boost the interest of researchers to work in this area in other proffer solutions to this problem bedeviling the financial system in Nigeria.

Ogbuji, Onuoha and Izogo (2012) investigated the the negative effects of the automated teller machine (ATM) as a channel for delivering banking services electronically in Nigeria. The samples for the study were collected from 600 respondents which were conveniently selected from Lagos and Anambra which were analyzed with the aid of chi-square. Findings from the study revealed that the ATM system has contributed to the increasing rate of fraud in the Nigerian banking sector and that it equally has an influence on the rate of expenditure of users in Nigeria.

In the study conducted by Olaleye and Fashina (2019) which focused on the nature of electronic banking related fraud on deposit money banks in Nigeria aimed at examining the effects and the controls put in place to prevent financial loss by Nigerian banks. Case study research design was used for data collected from the 2016 annual report of Nigerian Electronic Fraud Forum (NeFF). The study discovered that 2016 witnessed 19,531 fraud cases reported as against the 10,743 recorded in year 2015 and this represent 82% increase. The result also showed a significant relationship between electronic banking practices and the rate of increase in the security of banking transactions.

The study of Aigbe and Akpojaro (2014) provided a review on the different categories of electronic payment systems to access their level of security by classifying electronic payment systems into four categories: online electronic cash system, electronic cheque system, online credit card payment system, and smart cards

based electronic payment system. The study reviewed the online payment processes, authentication mechanisms, and authentication types. Findings of the study revealed that electronic payment systems with authentication mechanisms involving two or more authentication factors tend to be more secured, reduced fraud vulnerability, and boost users' confidence in using electronic payment systems.

Popoola (2013) examined the effect of trust on the adoption and usage of internet banking in Nigeria. The study interviewed 40 bank customers on security issue, bank reputation, information technology and institution based trust. Findings from the study revealed that bank customers in Nigeria lack trust in internet banking because of security issue, bank reputation, information technology and institution based trust.

Ibanichuka and Oko (2019) investigated the relationship between electronic frauds and financial performance of quoted banks on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study used ex-post-facto research design, descriptive, Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multivariate regression for data analysis. Results from the study revealed a negative and insignificant relationship between electronic fraud channels and financial performance.

Popoola, Fakunle, Omole, and Oyedeji (2018) examined the effect of bank fraud on Nigerian economy with the aim of highlighting the incidence and magnitude of fraud and some of its negative impact on the Nigeria economy. The study used field survey research methods and multiple linear regression analysis for the data collected from the financial statements of the selected banks. Finding from the study showed the existence of negative and significant relationships between bank fraud and economic development.

Theoretical Review

Related theories like triangle theory of fraud and diamond theory of fraud were reviewed

Theory of Fraud Triangle

In 1950, Donald Cressey, a criminologist, began the work on fraud, he believed that there must be a reason behind individual action. Cressey argued that the occurrence of fraud in any of these three factors: Pressure (Motivation), Opportunity and Rationalization. He referred to Pressure as the needs or desires that must be satisfied. This is later divided into financial pressure, work-related pressure and others. The second factor is the opportunity to commit fraud, conceal or avoid punishment from the fraud. Rationalization being the third factor involves giving unnecessary excuses to justify fraudulent act.

Theory of Fraud Diamond

Wolfe and Hermerson in 2004 came up with fraud diamond theory as a continuation of fraud triangle theory by adding a fourth dimension to fraud triangle. This theory argued that the occurrence of fraud is determined by individual's capability, personality trait and abilities. In addition to attractive forces of opportunity, pressure and rationalization to commit fraud, personal trait and ability to recognize the opportunity to perpetrate fraud were other essential factors that determine the occurrence of fraud.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

The study employed cross sectional survey research design which involves seeking responses from senior staff members of Ekiti State University chosen from the population of this study which consists of bank customers in Ekiti State.

Research Instruments

For the purpose of this study, questionnaire was used. The questionnaire was divided into four sections which are meant to provide answer to Personal data and various Research questions. One hundred questionnaires (100) were distributed to both Academic Staff and Non-Teaching Staff of Ekiti State University out of which seventy three (73) were recovered. The method employed for analysis of data through questionnaire administered to the respondents involved the use of logistic regression analysis.

Model Specification

The model for the study is specified below:

$$\text{Customer Trust} = f(\text{Electronic Fraud}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Decomposing electronic fraud, it can further be:

$$\text{Electronic Fraud} = \text{ATMF, MOBF, POSF, WEBF}$$

Therefore,

$$\text{CT} = f(\text{ATMF, MOBF, POSF, WEBF}) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

CT = Customer Trust

ATMF = Automated Teller Machine Fraud

MOBF = Mobile Banking Fraud

POSF = Point of Sale Fraud

WEBF = Website Purchase Fraud

Estimation Techniques

Logistic regression analysis was employed in the qualitative assessments of the impact of electronic fraud on customers trust.

Logit Equation

Logit equation looks like typical linear regression model

$$P_i = E(Y = 1 / X_i) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_i \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where

P_i = probability that $Y_i = 1$ (that is the event occurs)

β_1 = parameters to be estimated ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, 8$).

X = Electronic Fraud

Y = Customer's Trust = 1 if bank customers trust electronic payment channels and 0 if otherwise.

i = ith observation

Equation 3 can be written as:

$$P_i = E(Y = 1 / X_i) = 1 / 1 + e^{-(\beta_1 + \beta_2 X_i)} \dots \dots \dots 4$$

For case of exposition, equation 4 can be written as:

$$P_i = 1 / 1 + e^{-Z_i} = e^{Z_i} / 1 + e^{Z_i} \dots \dots \dots 5$$

Where $Z_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_i$

Equation 5 represents the cumulative logistic distribution function

P_i = the probability that bank customers trust all the electronic payment channels, the probability of not can be given as:

$$1 - P_i = 1 / 1 + e^{Z_i} \dots \dots \dots 6$$

Therefore, equation 6 can be written as:

$$P_i / 1 - P_i = 1 + e^{Z_i} / 1 + e^{-Z_i} = e^{Z_i} \dots \dots \dots 7$$

Where $P_i / 1 - P_i$ = the odds ratio in favour of customers trusting the payment channels.

Taken the natural log of equation 7, the model becomes:

$$L_i = \ln(P_i / 1 - P_i) = Z_i \dots \dots \dots 8$$

Z = the probability, which measures the total contribution of the independent variables in the model and is dependent variable.

$L = \log$ of the odds ratio, which is not only linear in X , but also linear in the parameters

For estimation of this model, eq. 8 becomes:

$$L_i = \ln(P_i / 1 - P_i) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_i + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots 9$$

(Gujarati 2013)

A priori Expectation

$$\frac{\partial CT}{\partial ATMF} < 0; \quad \frac{\partial CT}{\partial MOBF} < 0; \quad \frac{\partial CT}{\partial POSF} < 0; \quad \frac{\partial CT}{\partial WEBF} < 0;$$

Description of Variables

Automated Teller Machine Fraud (ATMF): This is electronic fraud through computerized machine that is stationed outside the bank premises and other strategic locations to render bank services to customers like cash withdrawal, cash transfer, bill payment, account statement and so on.

Mobile Banking Fraud (MOBF): This is the amount lost through mobile phone banking platform.

Point of Sale Fraud (POSF): This is the value lost by the use of POS machine at the spot of purchase as a means of payment for goods.

Web Purchase Services (WEB): This is the money lost through an electronic payment service rendered in the websites of service providers to bank customers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1 Demographic Characteristics

S/N	DETAILS	GROUPING	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	Gender	Male	23	31.5
		Female	50	68.5
2	Age	Below 30 years	23	31.5
		31-40	30	41.1
		41-50	13	17.8
		51-60	4	5.5
		Above 60	3	4.1
3	Educational Status	Post Graduate Degree	19	26.0
		Bachelor Degree	47	64.4
		Secondary	7	9.6
4	Marital Status	Married	32	43.8
		Single	41	56.2
5	Income	Between N50,000 to N100,000	39	53.4
		Between N110000 to N200000	17	23.3
		Between N210000 to N400000	15	20.5
		Above N400000	2	2.7

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2020

Table 1 showed that 31.5% respondents were male while 68.5% were female. Therefore, it could be inferred that majority of the respondents are female. The respondents' age revealed that 31.5% were below 30 years of age, 41.1% were within the age of 31-40 years, 17.8% were within the age of 41-50 years, 5.5% were within the age of 51-60 years, while 4.1% were within the age of 60 years and above. The survey showed that large proportions of the respondents were within the age of 31-40 years. Moreover, the educational status of the respondents revealed that 26% were post graduate degree holders, 64.4% were first degree graduate, 9.6% attained secondary school. It could be inferred that majority of the respondents were literate. The marital status of the respondents indicated that 43.8% of the respondents were married while 56.2% were single. However, result of the field survey also revealed that 53.4% earned between N50,000 to N100000, 23.3% earned between N110,000 to N200,000, 20.5% earned between N210,000 to N400000 while 2.7% earn N400000 and above.

Table 2 Summarizes Logit Model Estimate

Dependent: Customers Trust (CT)

Variables	Coefficient	Odd ratio	Probability
Constant	-8.447352	.0002145	0.010
ATMF	5.828549	339.8652	0.002
MOBF	-.7841655	.4565005	0.624
POSF	1.883837	6.578702	0.224
WEBF	-1.297204	.2732949	0.365

Source: Author's Computation, 2020

LR chi2(4) = 14.55

Prob > chi2 = 0.0057

Pseudo R2 = 0.1443

Table 2 presented the estimated coefficient, odd ratios and probability values of the explanatory variables which revealed that when other regressors are held constant, each slope coefficient measures the change in the estimated logit for a change in the value of the given regressor. The result revealed that ATMF has a coefficient of 5.828549 with a probability of 0.002 (2%), this implies that a unit increase in ATM fraud will lead to 5.828549 increase in the log odds of customers' trust indicating a positive and significant relationship. Also, MOBF has a coefficient of -.7841655, the implication is that when other variables are held constant, increase in mobile fraud will lead to decrease in the log odd of customers' trust by .7841655, this suggests a negative and insignificant relationship between the two. POS has a coefficient of 1.883837, implies that if the level of POS fraud increases, it will bring about 1.883837 increases in the log odds of Customers' trust. The coefficient of Website fraud depicts a negative coefficient of -1.297204 and a probability value of 0.365. This implies that a unit increase in the number of WEB fraud leads to a decrease of 1.297204 of the log odds of Customers' trust, this signifies a negative and insignificant relationship. However, the odds results gotten from the antilog of the various slope coefficients revealed a positive relationship to CT by exponentiate that ATMF, MOBF, POSF and WEBF have coefficients of 339.8652, .4565005, 6.578702 and .2732949 respectively. The implication is that for every additional increase in ATMF MOBF, POSF and WEBF the odds of CT will increase by 339.8652, .4565005, 6.578702 and .2732949 respectively.

The likelihood ratio statistics is 14.55 with probability value of 0.0057, this established that at least one of the regressions across the model is not simultaneously equal to zero, hence the model is fit for the analysis. Also, Mcfadden's Pseudo R-square that shows the change in terms of log likelihood from the intercept-only model to the estimates model is 0.1443 which indicates better fit.

Marginal Effect Test**Table 3 Marginal Effect Test**

Variables	dy/dx	Std. Err.	Probability
ATMF*	1.448454	.47617	0.002
MOBF*	-.1948732	.39732	0.624
POSF*	.468153	.38454	0.223
WEBF*	-.3223685	.3561	0.365

Source: Author's Computation, 2020

(*) dy/dx is for discrete change of dummy variable from 0 to 1

Table 3 presents the result of marginal effect test; this revealed that for every additional increase in ATMF and POSF, the probability of CT increase by 145% and 47%. Also, the marginal result for MOBF and POSF are 19% and 32% respectively. It implies that unit increase in mobile fraud and POS fraud will decrease the probability of CT by 19% and 32% respectively.

Post Estimation Test

Table 4 revealed that the model is rightly specified since the linear predicted value ($\hat{\mu}$) is significant while the linear predicted value squared ($\hat{\mu}^2$) has insignificant value. This showed that the link function is correctly specified (no specification error).

Table 4 Specification Test Result

CT	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Probability
_CONS	.1576873	.3167661	0.619
_HAT	1.056798	.3198681	0.001
_HATSQ	-.2048519	.2222014	0.357

Source: Author's Computation, 2020

LR $\chi^2(2) = 15.36$, Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0005$, Pseudo R² = 0.1523

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, findings from the result of logit regression analysis revealed that ATMF was significant and positively related to CT, while MOBF and WEBF were insignificant and negatively related to CT. Whereas, POSF exerted a positive and insignificant relationship with CT. Furthermore, mobile fraud and website fraud posed more threat to customers' trust in electronic payment channels than ATM and POS. To this end, the security of these platforms must be improved as well as other factors influencing customers trust in electronic payment channels.

The following recommendations will be useful in enhancing costumers' trust

- i. Banks should increase their security layers to reduce the activities of hackers, scammers and phishers. They should also ensure continuous enlightenment of customers on the need to safeguard their PINs and adhering strictly to rules and regulations guiding various payment channels as well as equipping them with latest antifraud technology in order to strengthen the security of the payment channels thereby enhancing customers' trust.
- ii. Customers should avoid replying unsolicited text messages and mails asking for their PINs and other personal questions that can reveal their details so as to guide against unauthorized access into their accounts.
- iii. The CBN should provide adequate security measures for various electronic banking channels.

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